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Editorial

Priority to the Person

When Pope Francis addresses the U.N. General Assembly on Sept. 15, 2020 he is expected to speak about the opportunity to rethink economic, political and environmental policies in a way that will benefit humanity and the earth, reports *CatholicPhylly*.

Since the corona pandemic began in early March, the pope has been urging individuals, organizations and governments to recognize the inequalities the pandemic has highlighted in economics and access to health care and education, as well as the ways current patterns of production and consumption have damaged the environment.

It may be remembered that Pope Francis began a series of general audience talks on Aug. 5, 2020 about the principles of Catholic social teaching that can help the world move forward in a way that is better for human beings and for the environment.

He spoke about transforming “the roots of our physical, spiritual and social infirmities and the destructive practices that separate us from each other, threatening the human family and our planet.”

During a news conference on August 26, 2020 in Rieti, Italy, to launch a celebration marking events in the life of St. Francis

of Assisi, Bishop Domenico Pompili hinted that “human fraternity,” a phrase used for a document on interreligious dialogue and cooperation signed in 2019 by Pope Francis and Sheikh Ahmad el-Tayeb, grand imam of al-Azhar.

According to *CatholicPhilly* it would make sense that a social encyclical on a post-COVID vision would build upon an affirmation that all human beings were created by God with equal dignity and that solutions to the world’s most pressing problems must be found together and must benefit all.

In an interview to Carlo di Cicco, former assistant editor of the Vatican newspaper, *L’Osservatore Romano*, Pietro Parolin, Vatican Secretary of State, said that “The priority is not the economy as such, but the human person”. He added that “COVID-19 not only provoked a health crisis but impacted multiple aspects of human life: the family, politics, labour, businesses, commerce, tourism, etc.” He noted further: “The broad and interconnected character of the pandemic constantly reminds us of the observation of Pope Francis that ‘everything is connected.’”

The cardinal affirmed that the idea “economy is not everything” is the only explanation for why so many national and local governments ordered lockdowns to prevent the spread of the coronavirus; “It shows that the priority isn’t the economy but the person.”

He added for the Catholic Church it is not enough to be concerned about a person’s physical health. “The integrity of the human person must be cared for,” which means caring for the person’s spiritual, political and economic health as well, he said.

Cardinal Parolin said, Catholic social teaching has emphasized the interdependence of nations, especially after St. John XXIII's 1963 encyclical *Pacem in terris* ("Peace on Earth"), which argued that there is a need for disarmament and that nuclear weapons.

The pandemic revealed "our common weakness, our shared fragility," he said. "However, instead of fostering cooperation for the universal common good, we see more and more walls rising around us, exalting borders as a guarantee of security and practicing systematic violations of the law, maintaining a situation of permanent global conflict.

"As Pope Francis recalled in Nagasaki (in November 2019), arms spending reached its peak in 2019, and now there is a serious risk that, after a period of decline, including due to pandemic-related restrictions, it will continue to increase," he said.

But, he said, the pandemic demonstrates that what is needed is "friendship and benevolence rather than hatred and fear." Catholic social teaching, the cardinal said, has firm biblical, theological and anthropological foundations and can be "continually updated" to respond to new needs and situations.

When speaking about the economy, he mentioned two most recent papal social encyclicals are key: Pope Benedict XVI's 2009 "Caritas in Veritate" ("Charity in Truth") and Pope Francis' 2015 "Laudato Si', On Care for Our Common Home."

"Benedict spoke of an economy in which room must be made for the logic of gift, the principle of gratuitousness, which expresses not only solidarity, but even more deeply human fraternity," the cardinal said. "Francis relaunched the theme of integral human development in the context of an 'integral

ecology,' one that is environmental, economic, social, cultural, spiritual."

"Today the pandemic is giving a tremendous shock to the entire economic and social system and its supposed certainties at all levels. The problems of unemployment are and will be dramatic; the problems of public health require the revolution of entire health and education systems; and the role of states and relations between nations are changing," Cardinal Parolin said.

"The church feels called to accompany the complicated journey that lies before us all as a human family," he said. "She must do so with humility and wisdom, but also with creativity," reports *CatholicPhilly*.

He added, "there are solid principles of reference, but today courageous creativity is more urgent than ever so that the dramatic crisis of the pandemic does not end in a terrible tragedy, but opens spaces for the human and ecological conversion that humanity needs."

May we learn from this pandemic our "our common weakness, our shared fragility," and move forward. May we foster cooperation for the universal common good. May we learn to respect the dignity of each person!

The Editor